

FEATURES OF TEACHING SCHOOLCHILDREN TECHNICAL TECHNIQUES IN BASKETBALL

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Annotation: The article defines the features of teaching basketball techniques to schoolchildren. The features of the psychophysiological and physical development of children of primary school age are analyzed, the results of studies on the influence of sports equipment with different characteristics on the technique of performing basketball game techniques by children of all ages are summarized.

Key words: schoolchildren, basketball, technical techniques, morphological characteristics, sports equipment.

Introduction. The national doctrine for the development of physical culture and sports, one of the priority tasks of the state in the field of physical education, determines the coverage of all children in the system of teaching the basic elements of certain sports. The development of effective methods for teaching physical exercise techniques in various sports, including basketball, is aimed at solving this problem [1, 3, 4].

A traditional problem in teaching basketball techniques at the initial training stage is the discrepancy between standard sports equipment and the physical capabilities of students. This problem is especially relevant in elementary schools. That is why a number of experts consider it advisable to start studying basketball techniques from the age of 11-12, or even later - from 13-15 years [2, 3, 5].

At the same time, the current physical education program provides for the study of elements of basketball from the 1st grade. There are a number of studies that scientifically substantiate the possibility of successful mastery of certain

basketball techniques by children 5-6 years old [6, 7, 9]. In addition, it has been established that children of primary school age are able to master the basic game techniques of basketball, but these exercises need to be studied in simplified conditions.

Currently, experts have calculated the value of the technical characteristics of basketball sports equipment, which is adapted to the physical capabilities of children 11 years old. Indicators of the technical characteristics of sports equipment adapted for girls of primary school age have also been determined. However, the results obtained are incomplete, contradictory and not confirmed experimentally.

The patterns of physical education cannot be identified without knowledge of the physiological foundations of human motor activity. A deep understanding of the mechanisms underlying age-related changes helps to avoid errors in the methodology, selection and dosage of physical exercises. To develop a methodology for teaching basketball to junior schoolchildren, age-related characteristics of the development of the mental, physiological and physical capabilities of the child's body, which determine the ability to master the basic elements of the game, become important.

An analysis of literary sources shows that the success of mastering basketball techniques is determined by a complex of individual characteristics of the child:

- functional state of organs and analytical systems;
- morphological features of the physique;
- level of development of speed and strength qualities;
- coordination abilities;
- efficiency in solving motor problems and tactical thinking;
- mental toughness [12, 13].

The basics of methods for teaching basketball techniques, which are used at the initial training stage, are widely presented in the scientific and methodological literature. Depending on the specifics of the application, these methods make it

possible to more or less successfully solve the main task of this stage - to form the fundamentals of basketball technique and tactics [10, 11].

Teaching basketball game techniques is based on the general principles of motor skill formation. In accordance with them, the process of studying individual technical techniques of the game consists of three stages, the duration of which depends on the specific learning conditions, the complexity of the technique and the selected methods.

The vast majority of methods provide for starting basketball training with a parallel study of the technique of individual playing techniques. It is recommended to study tactics both simultaneously with learning techniques, and a little later. In accordance with traditional teaching methods, it is advisable to learn any technique in the following sequence:

- 1) creating positive motivation for students;
- 2) creating a presentation about the reception;
- 3) studying the technique in simplified conditions;
- 4) study of reception in complicated conditions;
- 5) improvement of the learned technique in the game [14, 16, 17].

When studying a technique in simplified conditions, the main attention is supposed to be paid to mastering the correct structure of a motor action. To master the technique of playing basketball, traditional teaching methods involve performing a large number of underwater exercises. It is recommended to learn the basic technical techniques of the game by studying the exercise as a whole and in parts, as well as by the game method [18].

Studying a technique in complicated conditions involves its repeated execution with changes in the starting position, distance, direction of movement, speed of movement, with obstacles and confrontations. At this stage, significant attention is paid to studying the interactions between players. Improving the learned technique is carried out through educational and two-way games.

One of the characteristic features of traditional basketball teaching methods is the use of standard sports equipment. However, the size and weight of the ball, the height of the basket, the distance from the place of free throws to the backboard, and the size of the court are unreasonably large for primary school students to successfully master the technical elements of basketball.

This is due to the fact that in children of primary school age the main indicators of physical development differ significantly from similar indicators in adults [4, 5, 7]. That is, children 7-10 years old have to master motor actions in conditions that do not correspond to their physical capabilities. Under the influence of these factors, the characteristics of basketball techniques in children are significantly distorted. This concerns primarily the kinematic and dynamic characteristics of the equipment.

It should be emphasized that already at the stage of initial study, educational tasks for certain groups of students are inaccessible. The result of this is either the inability to perform certain motor actions at all, or their incorrect execution. Such exercises primarily include catching and passing the ball with one and two hands, throwing the ball with one and two hands. That is, already at the first stage of learning, students encounter difficulties that they themselves cannot cope with. This gives rise to despondency in their own abilities, significantly reduces interest in learning, and makes students passive participants in the educational process. This construction of the learning process contradicts the principles of accessibility, emotionality, consciousness and activity [3, 9].

At the same time, in the pedagogical process it is necessary to take into account that the process of ossification of the phalanges of the fingers of the upper limb is completed at 11 years, and the wrist - at 12 years. Therefore, another aspect of the problem of using traditional methods of teaching basketball techniques in elementary school is that the use of standard basketballs poses a certain danger for younger schoolchildren. It is associated with significant loads that fall on an unformed child's hand during dribbling, catching, passing and throwing an overly

heavy standard basketball. As a result, various injuries and hidden microtraumas are possible, which at the stage of initial study can cause children to have a negative attitude towards learning elements of technique and the game in general.

It should also be noted that a child's hand that is not fully formed quickly gets tired. Using standard basketballs speeds up this process in children 7-10 years old. Therefore, children make a large number of mistakes, because fatigue has a negative impact on the effectiveness of the process of learning motor actions, especially at the first stage.

The analysis of special scientific and methodological literature on the problems of physical education of children of primary school age allows us to assert that the level of development of mental, physiological and physical capabilities provides primary schoolchildren with the necessary prerequisites for the successful mastery of complexly coordinated movements, including basketball techniques.

The main components that determine the success of mastering basketball techniques are:

- morphological features of the physique;
- level of development of speed and strength qualities;
- coordination capabilities;
- functional state of organs and analytical systems;
- efficiency in solving motor problems and tactical thinking;
- mental toughness.

Conclusions. The effectiveness of the technique of performing basketball game techniques is determined by the following morphological characteristics of the performer: body length, length and width of the hand, finger span, length and span of the arms. The most informative indicator among these is body length, since this value determines the size of individual parts of the body and the level of development of motor qualities.

It has been established that the use of main support points and sports equipment adapted to the physical capabilities of schoolchildren contributes to

increasing the effectiveness of mastering coordinately complex motor actions. The main disadvantages of traditional methods used to study basketball in primary schools are the use of reproductive teaching methods and standard sports equipment that does not meet the physical capabilities of students.

References:

1. Karimovna, B. X. Methods of application and use of mobile games in the process of complex training of young handball players at the initial stage. *Creation of ethnographies with popular traditions*, 11(13), 14.
2. Karimova, B. X. The Effectiveness of the Use of Movement Games in the Early Training Phase of Young Handball Players. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 4(9), 172-175.
3. Karimovna, B. K., & Kushayevich, K. K. (2019). Development of physical culture and sports as the main factor social development of the young generation. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol*, 7(12).
4. Khaknazarov, K. K. (2024). Study of immunological reactivity, reproductive function and health of athletes. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 2(2), 154-160.
5. Kurbanovich, A. B. (2022). Increasing physical culture and sports skills. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(4), 77-78.
6. Амонтурдиев, Б. К. (2022). Физическая активность как один из факторов здорового образа жизни и воспитания молодежи. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(7), 283-292.
7. Амонтурдиев, Б. К. (2020). Анализ разбора стиля игры команды для контратаки в футболе. *Вестник науки и образования*, (7-2 (85)), 60-62.
8. Амонтурдиев, Б. К. (2020). Роль планирования тренировочного процесса и мотивации на успешный результат чемпионата. *Достижения науки и образования*, (9 (63)), 50-53.

9. Бердиева, Х. К. (2018). Современный ценностный потенциал физической культуры и спорта и пути его освоения обществом и личностью. *Вопросы педагогики*, (3), 23-25.
10. Бердиева, Х. К. (2019). Теоретические основы развития ловкости у детей 6-7 лет посредством подвижных игр и игровых упражнений с мячом. *Вопросы педагогики*, (5-2), 43-47.
11. Хакназаров, К. К., & Бердиева, Х. К. (2019). Современный ценностный потенциал физической культуры и спорта и пути его освоения обществом и личностью. *Вопросы педагогики*, (2), 111-113.
12. Хакназаров, К. К. (2020). Факторы, определяющие физическое воздействие в игре баскетбол. *Достижения науки и образования*, (10 (64)), 53-55.
13. Хакназаров, К. К., & Бердиева, Х. К. (2019). Основы формирования культуры движений младших школьников. *Вопросы педагогики*, (4-2), 225-228.
14. Хакназаров, К. К., & Бердиева, Х. К. (2019). Физиологические особенности, влияющие на развитие силовых способностей учащихся старших классов. *Вопросы педагогики*, (5-2), 326-329.
15. Умбаров, Д. М., & Хакназаров, К. К. (2020). Условия формирования профессиональной культуры у будущих учителей физического образования. *Вестник науки и образования*, (8-1 (86)), 82-84.
16. Усманходжаев, Т. С., Бердиева, Х. К., & Тошпулатова, А. Т. (2021). Двигательная активность и народные игры-эффективные средства, методы и формы организации физического совершенствования подрастающего поколения. *Евразийский союз ученых*, (1-1 (82)), 51-53.
17. Усманходжаев, Т. С., ДУ, У. Д. С., & Бердиева, Х. К. (2020). Роль подвижных игр в повышение двигательной активности детей. *Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий ва ўрта махсус таълим вазирлиги*, 647.